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Consumer Innovativeness In The Context Of Phygital Environments, Its Impact On Attitude And Use Intentions

Fijital Ortamlarda Tüketici Yenilikçiliği: Tutum ve Kullanım Niyeti Üzerindeki Etkisi

ABSTRACT

In contemporary retail environment, a steadily increasing digital orientation is observed. Even within physical retail formats, digital applications are increasingly integrated, leading to practices in which the physical and digital environments are intertwined. This study aims to examine consumers' perceptions of these practices referred to as "phygital" and to investigate their intention to adopt such emerging applications. The primary objective of this study is to explore consumers' attitudes toward phygital channels and their reasons for preferring phygital applications. Theory of Planned Behavior serves as the foundation for examining consumers' innovativeness, attitudes toward phygital retail applications and their intention to use such systems. In order to analyze the stated relationships through convenience sampling, data was collected from 374 respondents. The data was analyzed by SMART PLS 4. The findings show that social and hedonic consumer innovatives have positive relationship with attitude towards phygital applications. On the other hand, cognitive and social motivations of consumer innovativeness are not significantly related to attitude toward phygital tools. These results suggest that functional and hedonic aspects of novelties shall be communicated in phygital retail settings.

Keywords: Phygital, Consumer Innovativeness, Attitude, Use Intention, Theory of Planned Behavior

ÖZET

Günümüz perakende ortamında giderek artan bir dijital yönelim gözlenmektedir. Fiziksel perakende formatlarında dahi dijital uygulamaların daha yoğun şekilde entegre edildiği ve fiziksel ile dijital unsurların iç içe geçtiği uygulamalar yaygınlaşmaktadır. Bu çalışma, "fijital" olarak adlandırılan bu bütünleşik uygulamalara yönelik tüketici algılarını incelemeyi ve tüketicilerin bu yeni uygulamaları benimseme niyetlerini araştırmayı amaçlamaktadır. Araştırmanın temel amacı, tüketicilerin fijital kanallara yönelik tutumlarını ve bu tür uygulamaları tercih etme nedenlerini ortaya koymaktır. Bu çalışmada Planlı Davranış Teorisi, tüketicilerin yenilikçilik düzeyleri, fijital perakende uygulamalarına yönelik tutumları ve bu sistemleri kullanma niyetleri arasındaki ilişkilerin incelenmesi için kuramsal temel olarak kullanılmıştır. Belirtilen ilişkileri analiz etmek amacıyla kolayda örnekleme yöntemiyle 374 katılımcıdan veri toplanmıştır. Veriler SMART PLS 4 ile analiz edilmiştir. Bulgular, sosyal ve hedonik tüketici yenilikçiliğinin fijital uygulamalara yönelik tutum üzerinde pozitif bir etkisi olduğunu göstermektedir. Buna karşılık bilişsel ve fonksiyonel yenilikçilik boyutlarının fijital araçlara yönelik tutumla anlamlı bir ilişkisi bulunmamaktadır. Bu sonuçlar, fijital perakende bağlamında yeniliklerin sosyal ve hedonik yönlerinin ön plana çıkarılmasının tüketici tutumlarını güçlendirebileceğini göstermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Fijital, Tüketici Yenilikçiliği, Tutum, Kullanım Niyeti, Planlı Davranış Teorisi

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of phygital (physical + digital) arised to describe the convergence of digital and physical environments in the customer journey. Phygital retailing represents a retail phenomenon that combines physical and digital elements to deliver an interactive customer experience.

As the focus is moved away from separate individual channels to a wholesome consumer experience, phygital started receiving more attention. Along with the ever-changing technological advancements, the retail industry has become a playground equipped with new technologies trying to ameliorate the consumer journey. The future of marketing and retailing is being shaped around immersive technologies like artificial reality, virtual reality, interactivity, and real-time data integration.

Phygital retail applications are seen in many different formats. Consumers' reaction to these novelties is an important consideration for marketing. As in the case of any technological adaptation, consumer innovativeness is also very important in phygital environments adoption.

In this study, consumer innovativeness impact on attitude towards phygital and intention to use phygital applications.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Retailers develop new applications to respond to evolving customer needs and to create more engaging experiences. Early studies largely conceptualized phygital as an outgrowth of multichannel or omnichannel retailing, focusing primarily on the seamless alignment of physical store environments with digital touchpoints. Belghiti et al. (2017) were among the first to conceptualize the phygital shopping experience as a hybrid continuum in which physical and digital services and atmospherics jointly shape in-store experiences. The fusion of physical and digital encounters has been defined as an application that merges the characteristics of both formats within the same point-of-sale environment (Belghiti et al., 2017).

More recently, phygital experiences emphasize sensory immersion (sight, touch, sound, scent, taste), emotional engagement, and symbolic value as key components of phygital experiences. Batat (2024) introduced the phygital customer experience, arguing that phygital should not be reduced to channel integration but understood as a broader logic for orchestrating value co-creation across hybrid, multisensory, and technology-enabled touchpoints.

Around the world, there are many novel applications in the retail sector, some of which also gathered the attention of the academic world. Studies show that interactive in-store technologies like smart mirrors, AR try-on can enhance hedonic value, engagement, and memorability of shopping experiences (Batat & Hammedi, 2023).

One of the sectors that applies many novelties in phygital is sports apparel stores. Bonfanti et al. (2023) in their study suggested that applications creating interactivity, personalization, and gamification are driving memorable shopping experiences and influencing store patronage. Differentiation through customer experiences is of high importance for the luxury sector. Consequently, another sector pioneering the phygital applications is the luxury goods sector. Guzzetti et al. (2024) showed that phygital technologies reshape perceptions of luxury by balancing technological novelty with exclusivity and human contact.

In the Turkish literature, phygital marketing has been framed as a new era in marketing that strengthens brand–consumer interaction beyond conventional digital marketing, particularly through experiential and interactive technologies. In the Turkish real sector context, examples of phygital applications include digital ordering screens and product simulation technologies located inside physical stores. Güllü, Aşar, and Tüfek (2024) apply the Technology Acceptance Model to phygital marketing technologies used by tourism businesses. Perceived usefulness, ease of use, trust, and innovativeness are found to be significantly related to behavioral intention toward phygital tools.

Research conducted in other markets suggests that such combined physical and digital experiences provide value to customers in several ways (Batat & Hammedi, 2023). Through phygital retailing, customers benefit from the convenience of online search capabilities while also enjoying the flexibility of completing purchases in-store.

Banik (2023) examined hedonic factors (e.g., enjoyment, involvement) affecting store patronage in phygital retail and showed that involvement and experiential value strongly predict revisit intentions. Abd Malek (2023) explored how phygital retail factors influence attitudes toward phygital stores and subsequent purchase behavior in Malaysia.

Recent work also segmented consumers based on their phygital behaviors. Maciejewski (2025) developed a typology of consumers with distinct attitudes and behaviors toward phygital tools, illustrating heterogeneity in openness, involvement, and channel preferences.

When novelties, technological innovations are analyzed, the adoption of consumers to such new ways of doing things are very much affected by consumer innovations. Consumer innovativeness is typically defined as a consumer's tendency or predisposition to adopt new products, services, or ideas earlier than others in their social system. Early work in diffusion of innovations positions innovativeness as the key criterion underlying adopter categories in Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations framework. Consumer innovativeness is defined as the tendency of certain consumers to adopt new technologies more frequently and more rapidly than others (Midgley & Dowling, 1978). It is claimed to be a construct stimulating creative and innovation-oriented behavior and seen as a central element in studies on innovation diffusion (Roehrich, 2004).

Vandecasteele and Geuens (2010) introduced Motivated Consumer Innovativeness (MCI), a scale operationalizing innovativeness as a set of underlying motivations: functional, hedonic, social, and cognitive.

Functional Motivated Consumer Innovativeness represents a type of consumer innovativeness centered on ameliorating performance and efficiency in order to complete tasks and reach desired outcomes. It is grounded in task management and the pursuit of improved results (Vandecasteele & Geuens, 2010). Cognitive Motivated Consumer Innovativeness reflects an individual's motivation to pursue novel and intellectually stimulating experiences. Consumers with high levels of cognitive MCI adopt new technologies to fulfill cognitive goals such as discovery, comprehension, and intellectual challenge. It motivates consumers to engage with new technological offerings to stimulate their thinking, explore new ideas, understand intricate concepts, and foster creative insight. Socially motivated consumers often look for social approval when making choices, which increases their likelihood of trying a new technology when they observe others in their social circle adopting it (Ingham et al., 2015). Hedonic MCI reflects the degree to which consumers are driven to adopt and use innovative products or services for experiential or pleasure-oriented reasons, such as enjoyment, excitement, or sensory gratification.

Vandecasteele & Geuens (2010) claimed that these motivational dimensions predict innovative purchase intentions better than traditional innovativeness measures. The key components of the theoretical framework of this study are derived from a simplified version of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). TPB offers a robust structure for assessing attitudes toward phygital tools usage, as well as corresponding intentions (Ajzen, 1991). Central to TPB is the assumption that consumers' innovativeness in using phygital tools is the primary determinant of their engagement in such behavior.

In this study, based on the theory of planned behavior, the effects of motivational innovation factors are analyzed.

The hypotheses are developed as;

H1. Social motivation on consumer innovativeness positively affects attitude towards using phygital applications.

H2. Functional motivation on consumer innovativeness positively affects attitude towards using phygital applications.

H3. Cognitive motivation on consumer innovativeness positively affects attitude towards using phygital applications.

H4. Hedonic motivation on consumer innovativeness positively affects attitude towards using phygital applications.

H5. Attitude towards using phygital applications positively affects intention to use.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study employed a quantitative research design using a questionnaire survey. The questionnaire consists of two sections. The first section included the scale items, as seen in the table below, while the second section had demographic questions. The original scales were translated into Turkish and adapted to the research context. All constructs were measured using a five-point Likert-type scale

Data was collected through online questionnaires administered to consumers who have encountered or used phygital applications, using convenience sampling.

Table 1. Scales Used in the Research

Construct	Source	Number of Items
Motivated Consumer Innovativeness	Vandecasteele & Geuens (2010)	20
Attitude Toward Phygital	Balakrishnan & Dwivedi (2021)	3
Intention to Use	Salisbury et al. (2001)	3

4. FINDINGS

A total of 374 respondents were reached after elimination of the missing data. 60% of the respondents were female, 80% were graduates.

Quantitative data analysis using Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with SmartPLS 4 was used to test the structural model. PLS-SEM was used based on its ability to handle complex models with formative and reflective indicators, exemption of the data normality requirement (Hair & Alamer, 2022). The structural model tested hypotheses of the conceptual framework.

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted using PLS-SEM. According to Afthanorhan (2013) PLS-SEM path modeling using SMARTPLS is useful for confirmatory factor analysis as it is more reliable and valid.

The reliability of constructs are tested by composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha ($>.70$). Convergent validity was estimated by calculating the average variance extracted (AVE) (Hair et al., 2022). As reliability thresholds are CR above 0.70 and AVE above 0.5. All scales were reliable, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Factor Loadings & Reliability

		Attitude	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Attitude	AT1	0.913	0.869	0.869	0.920	0.793
	AT2	0.889				
	AT3	0.869				
Cognitive Innovativeness	CI1	0.759	0.879	0.879	0.912	0.675
	CI2	0.831				
	CI3	0.849				
	CI4	0.856				
	CI5	0.809				
Functional Innovativeness	FI1	0.798	0.876	0.881	0.915	0.730
	FI2	0.901				
	FI3	0.879				
	FI4	0.836				
Hedonic Innovativeness	HI1	0.825	0.923	0.928	0.942	0.765
	HI2	0.890				
	HI3	0.898				
	HI4	0.911				
	HI5	0.846				
Use Intention	UI1	0.897	0.875	0.875	0.923	0.800
	UI2	0.909				
	UI3	0.876				
Social Innovativeness	SI2	0.872	0.846	0.855	0.897	0.686
	SI3	0.843				
	SI5	0.744				
	SI1	0.846				

The Fornell-Larcker criterion was used for testing the validity. Table 3 shows that the square root of the AVE is higher than the inter-construct correlation, showing good discriminant validity. Also, another discriminant validity criterion is the heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) correlation ratio, in which all values are smaller than 0.90. Therefore, discriminant validity is established for this model.

Table 3: Fornell-Larcker

	Attitude	Cogn. Inv	Func. Innov.	Hedonic	UseIntent	Social Innov.
Attitude	0.891					
Cognitive	0.461	0.821				
Functional Innovativeness	0.515	0.675	0.854			
Hedonic	0.574	0.681	0.706	0.874		
Usage Intention	0.814	0.469	0.526	0.581	0.894	
Social Innovativeness	0.459	0.520	0.580	0.656	0.479	0.828

Table 4: HTMT

	Attitude	Cogn. Inv	Func. Innov.	Hedonic	UseIntent	Social Innov.
Attitude						
Cognitive	0.528					
Functional Innovativeness	0.587	0.770				
Hedonic	0.637	0.756	0.783			
PIntention	0.902	0.534	0.599	0.643		
Social Innovativeness	0.533	0.603	0.672	0.738	0.554	

After obtaining satisfactory results regarding the reliability and validity of the measurement model, the structural model was analyzed using PLS SEM.

Figure 1: Path Analysis

Table 5: Standardized theoretical path coefficients

	Standardized Estimates	T (O/STDEV)	P values	Hypothesis
Attitude -> UseIntention	0.814	34.614	0.000	H5: Supported
Cognitive -> Attitude	0.054	0.864	0.194	H1: Not Supported
Functional Innovativeness -> Attitude	0.174	2.794	0.003	H2: Supported
Hedonic -> Attitude	0.348	5.364	0.000	H3: Supported
Social Innovativeness -> Attitude	0.103	1.501	0.067	H4: Not Supported

The path analysis results showed 3 out of 5 hypotheses were statistically supported. Cognitive motivation ($\beta = 0.054, p .194$) and social motivation of consumer innovativeness ($\beta = 0.103, p ,067$) had no significant influence on attitude. Thus, Hypotheses 1 and 4 were not supported. In addition, attitude played an important role in the formation of intentions to use ($\beta = 0.814, p,000$).

Cognitive MCI refers to an individual’s desire for new and stimulating experiences that stimulate the brain. Phygital applications might be seen as not breakthrough innovations, triggering the desire to learn, accomplish new tasks. In Turkey, currently, the phygital tools used are very much limited to fast payment or order options. Therefore, the insignificant influence of cognitive MCI can be attributed to limited technological novelty in phygital settings. Social MCI’s impact on attitude is also not found to be significant. One of the underlying triggers of social motivation is to differentiate oneself from others and express individualism. As discussed before, since the majority of the current phygital applications may not be seen as a tool to symbolize individuality, the impact of social MCI on attitude towards it is not found to be significant. Functional and hedonic MCIs, on the other hand, have been found to have a significant positive effect on attitude towards phygital.

5. CONCLUSION

This study analyzed the impact of motivational consumer innovativeness on attitudes towards phygital. Also, the study analyzed the relationships of the constructs of the theory of planned behavior. This study provides significant managerial implications for retailers considering phygital tools applications. The importance of functional motivation for attitudes toward phygital should be underlined. It is essential to provide flawless, efficient service through phygital applications. Secondly, the fun and excitement attribute of phygital applications shall be communicated.

This study, by focusing on a newly invested and growing technological trend, phygital applications presented theoretical and managerial contributions, but there are also limitations. Firstly, the study was conducted in Türkiye, a future multi-cultural study would shed light on cultural differences in motivated consumer innovativeness. Secondly the study shall be repeated when the phygital applications become more common and more complex.

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